

Imaging the Mantle Transition Zone Using Integrated Geophysical-Petrological Modelling of Fundamental and Overtone Surface Wave Dispersion Data

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Abstract

Surface wave dispersion curves, including both fundamental modes and overtones, are crucial tools for constraining the structure of the upper mantle and mantle transition zone. The fundamental mode is most sensitive to shallower structures, typically within the lithosphere and upper asthenosphere, while higher overtones penetrate deeper, providing valuable sensitivity to the transition zone and even the uppermost lower mantle. By jointly modelling both fundamental and overtone dispersion data, we can achieve improved resolution of key features such as the lithosphere-asthenosphere boundary, the 410 km and 660 km discontinuities, and variations in thermal and compositional structure. Here we present a through sensitivity analysis of fundamental and overtone Rayleigh and Love surface wave dispersion data to the in situ thermochemical structure in a thermodynamically self-consistent framework. The effect of temperature and chemical composition variations, and hence the associated seismic velocities and density fields, at different depths alongside with the topography of the 410 km and 660 km transition zone mineral phase discontinuities are systematically analysed. Our preliminary results indicate that both fundamental mode and overtone dispersion curves are highly sensitive to the upper mantle structure, in particular, to the 660 km discontinuity where a strong contrast in seismic velocities and densities is present in our thermodynamic modelling. In the uppermost lower mantle (down to 1500 km) the fundamental mode is only affected after periods of 200 s, whereas the overtones are significantly affected at all significant periods (20 to 150 s). Furthermore, thermochemical anomalies in the uppermost lower mantle influence Love and Rayleigh wave dispersion differently. Our preliminary results suggest that the addition of overtones to the fundamental mode data can improve the resolution of mantle transition zone models so far as the the uppermost lower mantle structure (down to 1500 km) is also included in the thermochemical models for consistency.